

Mergers, Acquisitions and Innovation: Measuring Heterogenous Innovation Incentives for Acquirers and Targets

Adrian Er

Economics BSc (Hons)

23rd April 2025

Abstract

In the context of rising concerns over mergers impacting innovation incentives, this work evaluates the impact of mergers on the growth of R&D expenditures and R&D intensities for 277 acquiring firms and 27 target firms between 1997 and 2023. Employing various matching techniques to construct appropriate control groups, a difference-in-differences framework is applied to estimate the causal effects of mergers on post-merger R&D growth and R&D intensity. The results indicate that, in the year following a merger, acquiring firms exhibit a significant increase in R&D growth, possibly reflecting a "big push" to integrate the target firms' innovative capabilities. However, most other estimated effects, including changes in R&D intensities, are statistically insignificant, suggesting that the broader impact of mergers on innovation incentives remains ambiguous.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor Dr. Ron Lavi for his guidance and assistance throughout my research project work.

I would also like to extend my thanks to Dr. Florian Szücs (WU Vienna University of Economics and Business) for his valuable suggestions during the data collection process.

Data and Code

All data and codes used in this dissertation are available from the link provided below. For context and instructions on usage, please refer to the accompanying “*read_me.txt*” files.

<https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/3qc8gct0nnk1xya5mgb74/ANoB2zyL3rObRMChngYVPx0?rlkey=nfd2lo6az6qw6o72y4o039j6q&st=od12hg1c&dl=0>

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1 Introduction

The European Commission's (EC)'s approach to assessing the effects of mergers on innovation is a key policy change championed by Margrethe Vestager, the now-former European Commissioner. In a 2024 speech to the International Bar Association, Vestager emphasised that EU merger control rules exist, in part, "to protect innovation" (Vestager, 2024). This statement aligns with the rise of a novel theory of harm, which argues that mergers can "lead to a reduction of innovation" in an industry (Schulz, et al., 2018). A notable example of this notion is in the EC's review of the Dow-DuPont merger, where the EC concluded that the merger would significantly reduce innovation competition in the pesticide sector. As a result, DuPont's global R&D organisation in pesticides was divested to allow for the merger's clearance (EC, 2017).

The goal of this study is to contribute to the empirical discussion on the relationship between mergers and the incentive for acquirers and targets to conduct innovation efforts. An important aspect of this research is the explicit differentiation between acquirers and targets, a contrast that previous studies have often neglected. Many studies pool the data for both groups or assume targets as being affected symmetrically to acquirers. However, as shown in this study, acquirers and targets differ in size and pre-merger R&D expenditures. Failing to account for this distinction risks overlooking significant sources of heterogeneity in innovation incentives. A distinction between any effects on acquirers and targets may also prove useful for competition authorities when considering behavioural or structural remedies for mergers which raise competition concerns.

Furthermore, while existing studies tend to focus on mergers within specific industries or countries, this study broadens the sample to include mergers in various sectors. This approach aims to identify whether general effects of mergers on innovation exist.

This study focuses on two R&D input metrics: the growth of R&D expenditure and R&D intensity, defined as the ratio of R&D expenditure to revenue. By analysing R&D inputs rather than outputs (such as patents or new products), this study assesses a firm's willingness to invest in innovation, rather than their success in achieving it – although R&D inputs and

outputs are often highly correlated (Hagedoorn and Cloudt, 2003) so the results may also be indicative of output-based measures.

In terms of methodology, this study is based on that of Szücs (2014) – which follows the suggestions of Blundell and Dias (2000) – to combine matching techniques with difference-in-differences (DiD) estimation. The approach compares the R&D growth and intensity of acquirers and targets with firms not involved in the mergers but otherwise share similar characteristics. Various matching techniques are used to construct different control groups to evaluate the robustness of the results.

The findings indicate that acquirers increase R&D growth in the year following a merger, suggesting a “big push” to incorporate the innovative activities of target firms and commercialise the innovative endeavours. However, most other results are statistically insignificant, indicating that changes in R&D growth for targets and R&D intensity for both acquirers and targets are ambiguous.

This dissertation is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the theoretical and empirical literature on mergers and innovation. Section 3 details the dissertation’s data and empirical strategy. Section 4 presents the results, which are discussed further in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes and provides direction for future research on the topic.

2 Theory and Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Overview of the Impact of Mergers on Innovation

Before discussing existing literature investigating the impact of mergers on innovation, it is helpful to introduce the varying theoretical perspectives on the topic. The theory is outlined in Veugelers (2006), where arguments are categorised to be from industrial organisation literature and corporate governance literature. Below, the key arguments from Veugelers (2006) are outlined.

Arguments from industrial organisation literature are equivocal. On the one hand, mergers can eliminate wasteful R&D duplication between acquirers and targets. While this may decrease R&D inputs, it does not necessarily reduce R&D outputs. Additionally, by reducing the number of competitors, mergers may increase the appropriability of innovation, which means that firms have a greater ability to capture the returns on their technological innovations. With reduced knowledge spillover, the incentive to innovate may increase. Mergers may also enhance R&D efficiency through economies of scale; larger firms can spread risks across a broader portfolio of projects and gain access to greater capital resources. This can lead to higher R&D outputs with fewer inputs, giving merged firms an advantage compared to their activities in their pre-merger state.

On the other hand, merged firms could face diseconomies of scale in R&D. Increased bureaucratic pressures and monitoring activities can hinder flexibility and slow down innovative efforts. Additionally, smaller firms often benefit from greater adaptability, enabling them to respond more quickly to external opportunities. Mergers may also reduce R&D competition; when firms coordinate their R&D investment strategies, overall investment levels may decline. Furthermore, if the market already has high appropriability, fewer competitors may weaken the incentive to innovate.

The relationship between market power and R&D investment is also ambivalent. Higher market power may discourage innovation, as firms fear cannibalising their existing products. An opposing view is that larger and dominant firms may increase their R&D efforts to defend their profits from nascent competitors.

Corporate governance literature, on the other hand, is more vocal towards arguments which claim that mergers reduce innovation. This is due to several factors. First, mergers demand significant attention from an acquirer's management, which reduces their focus on R&D projects. Second, the financial costs of acquiring another firm can limit capital available for future innovation. Third, after a merger, managers may become more risk-averse, making them less likely to invest in uncertain innovative projects. Finally, increased debt from an acquisition can make R&D investments less attractive from a tax perspective.

In summary, industrial organisation literature argues that the innovation of merging firms can both increase and decrease following a merger. However, corporate governance literature is unambiguous and argues that innovation decreases following a merger.

2.2 Literature Review of the Impact of Mergers on Innovation

Due to the plethora of theoretical impacts of mergers on innovation, many empirical studies assume an agnostic stance on their expectations (Szücs, 2014). Below is a discussion of the existing empirical studies.

Szücs (2014), which forms the empirical foundation of this study, analyses the effects of mergers on both acquirers and targets, to account for potential heterogeneous effects between the two groups. The study is not limited to specific industries or countries; instead, it uses a large sample of acquirers and targets from mergers investigated by the EC and the Federal Trade Commission (FTC). By applying various matching methods and DiD estimators, Szücs finds that target firms decrease R&D efforts after a merger. Meanwhile, the R&D intensity of acquirers drops due to an increase in sales after the acquisition. The broad scope of the sample, covering multiple industries, makes the findings generalisable to a wider scope of mergers. Additionally, Szücs accounts for structural zeros in R&D expenditures allowing for the inclusion of non-innovative firms in the analysis. This is something that other studies have not implemented which limits their ability to find effects beyond firms that were already innovative pre-merger.

Using a similar econometric approach to the above, Ornaghi (2009) investigates the impact of 27 mergers on various R&D input and output metrics, focusing solely on the pharmaceutical industry. Ornaghi finds that, in a pooled analysis of acquirers and targets, innovative efforts decrease post-merger. Ornaghi also accounts for endogeneity related to technological relatedness before the merger but finds that this factor is not associated with better R&D outcomes post-merger. While focusing on the pharmaceutical industry has merits, given the high number of large mergers in this sector that have raised policy concerns citing negative effects on innovation (Haucap, et al., 2019), it may be more insightful to analyse acquirers and targets separately, rather than pooling them together. As outlined earlier, such a distinction may prove useful for competition authorities when considering any remedies for supposedly anti-competitive mergers.

Stiebale and Reize (2011) reports similar findings to those above, based on a sample of 304 small- and medium-sized German firms and foreign acquisitions, whilst also accounting for structural zeros.

Focusing on sample of 217 US firms in the electronic and electrical equipment industries, Blonigen and Taylor (2000), finds a strong negative correlation between R&D intensity and a firm's decision to engage in acquisitions. These results suggest that firms used in the authors' sample either specialise in "making" or "buying" technology via acquisitions. These results can be combined with those of Hitt, et al. (1991), which finds that acquisitive growth has a negative impact on innovation inputs (R&D intensity) and outputs (patent intensity). The authors conclude that their results support the notion that mergers reduce managers' willingness to pursue innovative activities. When combining the results of these two studies, it can be inferred that firms more inclined to "buying" technology through acquisitions pose a greater threat to innovation via mergers than firms which "make" technology.

Other studies, however, find an increase in innovative activity following mergers. Using a sample of 123 French firms acquired by non-domestic acquirers, Bertrand (2009) finds that mergers increase R&D expenditures for the French firms. Similarly, Stiebale (2013) finds a positive effect on R&D levels for acquiring firms, based on a sample of 324 German firms. Stiebale's study also finds that the positive effects are more pronounced for acquirers in high-tech and innovative industries. Finally, Cefis, et al. (2009) analyses the impact of alliances between groups of firms, which may mimic the properties of mergers. The authors find that

members of an alliance have higher aggregate R&D expenditures than independent firms – although independent firms exhibit greater R&D efficiency.

All studies discussed so far show that the impacts of mergers on innovation metrics are mixed. The sample of firms and mergers used in each study varies, which highlights that the effects of mergers on innovation are heterogeneous.

Ahuja and Katila (2001) distinguishes between acquisitions with the primary aim of technology transfer (technological acquisitions) and non-technological acquisitions. Using a sample of 72 chemical companies and 534 acquisitions, the authors find that non-technological acquisitions have no impact on innovation outputs, while technological acquisitions improve innovation outputs. The extent of improvement depends on the relatedness of the two merging parties. Cloudt, et al. (2006) expands this approach to four major high-tech sectors. While their results largely align with those of Ahuja and Katila (2001), the authors find a negative impact on acquiring firms' post-merger innovative performances for non-technical acquisitions. Together, these results suggest that the rationale for a merger impacts post-merger innovation, and that perhaps there are economies of scale and/or increased appropriability that enhance innovation in technological acquisitions.

Desyllas and Hughes (2010) finds that after a merger, R&D intensities initially drop for acquirers but rise again after the third-year post-merger. This is based on a sample of 2624 high-tech US acquisitions. The authors show that when acquirers and targets are technologically related, R&D productivity increases post-merger, whereas it decreases when they are technologically unrelated. Cassiman, et al. (2005) extends this argument by distinguishing between technological relatedness and market relatedness, with a sample of 31 mergers. In contrast to Desyllas and Hughes (2010), the authors find that mergers between parties with complementary technologies improve R&D performances, whereas when merged entities are technologically substitutive, R&D levels are significantly reduced. These studies emphasise the heterogeneous effects of mergers on R&D based on the relatedness between the acquirer and target.

Bertrand and Zuniga (2006) examines the impact of mergers on R&D expenditures at the industry level, differentiating between domestic and cross-border mergers. At the aggregate level, the authors find no significant relationship between mergers and R&D spending.

However, they observe that domestic mergers have a positive effect on R&D spending in low-tech industries and that they negatively impact R&D spending in medium-tech industries. In contrast, cross-border mergers have a positive impact on R&D spending in medium-tech industries. This study provides an interesting result, implying that domestic and cross-border mergers differ in their impact on R&D investment, which could highlight that the rationale for a merger impacts R&D investments.

Hsu, et al., (2021) also looks at foreign takeovers, finding that innovative firms from countries deemed as less innovative produce more patents and invest more in R&D after they acquire targets in countries deemed as highly innovative.

Several studies have expanded empirical research to look at the impact of mergers on the competitors of the merging parties. Such analyses prove useful in policy debates because competition authorities seek to maintain competition in the entire product market following a merger. Using a sample of 63 listed pharmaceutical firms, Valentini (2016) finds a negative correlation between merger activity and the innovation of competitors. Valentini defines rival firms based on the technological proximity of their patent portfolios. Haucap, et al. (2019) follows a similar approach but uses EC decision documents to define competitors based on expert analyses and definitions. The authors find negative effects of mergers on competitors' innovation in markets with high R&D intensities and where technology classes of acquirers and targets overlap in their pre-merger innovation activities. However, while these studies seek to provide valuable insights, they may suffer from potential biases. Large pharmaceutical firms often compete in multiple product markets, making them competitors to many mergers. This makes it challenging to isolate the impact of a single merger on a major competitor, likely resulting in biased conclusions. Additionally, analysing the effects of multiple mergers within a short period tends to limit the sample to smaller pharmaceutical firms that are not competitors in more than one merger, meaning treatment effects may not apply to all firms.

2.3 Summary of Literature Review

The findings of the empirical studies discussed above are summarised in Table 1. As highlighted by these studies – and the theory outlined earlier – the impact of mergers on

innovation is mixed. However, most conclude a weak negative relationship between mergers and innovation metrics.

Table 1 Summary of prior studies

Study	Sample	Findings
Szücs (2014)	265 acquirers 133 targets	R&D intensity of acquirers drops Targets decrease R&D efforts post-merger
Ornaghi (2009)	27 acquisitions	Decrease in R&D efforts and performance
Stiebale and Reize (2011)	304 targets	Decrease in target R&D
Blonigen and Taylor (2000)	217 acquirers	Negative correlation between R&D intensity and acquisition engagement
Hitt, et al. (1991)	191 acquisitions	Negative impact on R&D intensity and patent intensity
Bertrand (2009)	123 targets	Increase in R&D expenditure for targets
Stiebale (2013)	324 acquirers	R&D expenditure increases especially for acquirers in innovative industries
Cefis, et al. (2009)	3696 firms	Alliances increase R&D expenditure but decrease R&D efficiency
Ahuja and Katila (2001)	72 acquirers	Technology-driven mergers increase R&D output
Cloodt, et al. (2006)	347 acquirers	Non-technical acquisitions decrease R&D performance
Desyllas and Hughes (2010)	2624 acquirers	R&D intensity initially drops but rises after the third year
Cassiman, et al. (2005)	31 acquisitions	Technologically complimentary mergers increase R&D performance Technologically substitutive mergers decrease R&D levels
Bertrand and Zuniga (2006)	50000 acquisitions	Cross-border mergers have a positive effect on R&D for medium-tech industries but negatively affect R&D for low-tech industries
Hsu, et al., (2021)	85591 acquisitions	Acquisitions by firms from low innovation countries of firms from high innovation countries increases R&D performance
Valentini (2016)	63 firms	Negative impact on innovation of competitors
Haucap, et al. (2019)	65 mergers	Negative impact on innovation of competitors in high R&D intensity markets

As explained in Section 3.1, this study builds upon that of Szücs (2014) by extending the analysis to incorporate mergers up to 2024 – but only mergers notified to the EC.

3 Data and Empirical Strategy

3.1 Data

This study builds upon the framework and methodology used in Szücs (2014), which examines how mergers impact R&D growth and intensity for both acquiring and target firms. Szücs uses a sample of mergers investigated by the EC and the FTC between 1990 and 2009. To establish causal relationships, Szücs uses various matching techniques to construct control groups and then applies DiD estimators to measure the effects of mergers on the two R&D metrics.

For this study, we created a dataset of all mergers notified to the EC between 1997 and 2023.¹ In contrast to Szücs (2014), this sample is limited to EC-investigated mergers because the EC publicly communicates all merger notifications that meet its investigative thresholds,² whereas the FTC only publishes communications of a subset of notified mergers which it chooses to investigate.³ The created sample contains mergers which were notified to the EC by companies headquartered in 31 different nations,⁴ operate in many different product markets⁵ and were either cleared or subject to conditions by the EC. The only common factor in these mergers is that they were significant enough to meet the EC's notification thresholds. Therefore, the sample is focused on major transactions which require regulatory clearance. To prevent confounding effects from multiple transactions by the same acquirer, firms which had engaged in multiple acquisitions within a four-year period are excluded. This approach ensures that the observed changes in R&D can be attributed to a single merger event rather than being influenced by overlapping effects from sequential acquisitions.

¹ Accounting data was available from 1995 to 2024, so the analysis focuses on mergers from 1997 to 2023. This ensures access to the accounting data of merging parties at least one-year before and one-year after the merger, including the R&D growth rate. The sample does not include simplified procedures and is limited to mergers with only two named parties.

² See Article 1 of the "the EC Merger Regulation" for a complete set of merger notification thresholds.

³ See Kovacic, et al. (2014) for a comparison of the EU and US competition authorities' approaches to merger control.

⁴ Despite limiting the sample to EC cases, 30% of the merging parties are headquartered in the US. See Appendix A for the distribution of countries of headquarters in the sample.

⁵ The firms in the sample are classified by 37 different 2-digit US SIC codes. See Appendix A for the distribution of industries in the sample.

We combined the dataset of mergers with financial statement data containing the R&D expenditures of the merging parties and other metrics (total assets, net income, revenue and total debt), as well as organisational characteristics (employee count, headquarter location, founding year and 2-digit US SIC codes).

Initially, financial data for merging parties was sourced from LSEG Workspace (formerly known as the Thomson Reuters Worldscope database, which was used by Szücs). To link each acquirer and target to their corresponding financial data – where available – we initially considered using a fuzzy matching approach. This technique attempts to match similar merging party names with the names of companies with available financial data based on the sequence and similarity of characters. However, this method proved insufficient in many cases. For example, a fuzzy matching algorithm fails to link “Google” to its financial data under the parent company name “Alphabet” due to the lack of character similarity. As a result, many relevant matches were missed.

To address this limitation, we decided to manually match data which meant searching for each acquirer and target individually within LSEG Workspace to identify whether their financial information was available. Given the size of the dataset (approximately 4,000 companies), the manual search was initially completed for the first 2,000 entities. However, this approach also encountered a significant obstacle: LSEG Workspace lacked financial data for a sizeable portion of the companies in the dataset. This resulted in the usable sample being smaller than anticipated.

Following the challenges with data availability, we sought advice from Florian Szücs – the author of Szücs (2014). Szücs recommended using Moody’s Orbis (formerly Bureau van Dijk Orbis), noting that it may offer more a complete coverage of European firms compared to LSEG Workspace. In addition to broader coverage, Moody’s Orbis includes a feature that allows users to upload a list of companies – in our case, the acquirers and targets in the dataset – and automatically checks for the availability of financial data for each entity. This tool significantly improved the efficiency of the matching process.

We took the data from Orbis and supplemented it with data from S&P Capital IQ Pro where certain firm-specific characteristics, such as headquarter locations, were missing. After observations for which R&D expenditures were not available in the years preceding and

proceeding the merger were excluded, the subsequent sample contained 329 acquirers and 60 targets. There are more acquirers than targets in the sample because post-merger financial data for targets is only available if the target continues to exist post-acquisition.⁶

Next, we manually verified that the financial data was matched to the correct companies by Orbis' automated matching tool. This step aimed to eliminate potential type I errors, where Orbis may have incorrectly linked financial data to the wrong acquirer/target. While type II errors – where a company is not matched to any financial data despite it being available on Orbis – may still exist, we believe that these instances are not systematic and are therefore unlikely to introduce bias into the results. After completing these manual checks, the final sample consisted of 277 acquirers and 27 target firms.

We used Pitchbook to find the year of which the mergers were completed.

When checking for the completeness of R&D data, companies that explicitly reported *zero* R&D expenditures were included and those with *missing* R&D data were excluded (see Section 3.5 on structural zeros).

This sample of merging firms is complemented with a large sample of potential controls created by finding all other firms on Moody's Orbis that report R&D expenditures but are not in the merger dataset. Relevant control groups are constructed from these potential controls. Since the set of potential controls is around 50 times larger than the set of merging firms, we are confident that a close match can be found for each treatment observation. For all potential controls, we collected the same financial statement metrics and organisational characteristics as we did for the merging parties.

For both merging parties and controls' data, all values were standardised to US dollars. We then calculated the R&D growth rate (defined as the percentage change in R&D expenditures between two consecutive years),⁷ the R&D intensities (defined as the ratio of R&D

⁶ For a discussion of how structural integration versus structural separation of acquired firms affects innovation outcomes post-merger, see Puranam and Srikanth (2007).

⁷ Where R&D expenditures remained at zero over two consecutive periods, R&D growth was set to zero. R&D growth rates were capped at 1 to avoid instances where preceding R&D expenditures were zero and R&D expenditures in the preceding year were non-zero.

expenditures to revenue)⁸ and profitability (defined as the ratio of net income to total assets) for all firms in all years. Logs were taken of the total assets, revenues, employee count and total debt variables, with one added to all zero values before the transformation.

Table 2 shows summary statistics of the acquiring and target firms in the years prior to and proceeding the merger as well as those of the potential control firms. Figure 1 presents the distribution of acquirer and target occurrences within our sample period.

Table 2. Summary statistics for the pre- and post-merger years for acquirers and targets and potential controls.

	Acquirers		Targets		Controls
	Before	After	Before	After	All years
R&D intensity	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03
R&D growth	0.04	0.11	0.01	0.08	0.03
Profitability	0.07	0.05	0.03	0.06	0.01
Total assets	23.23	23.59	21.80	22.09	18.50
Revenue	23.09	23.32	21.67	21.88	17.21
Employee count	10.31	10.48	9.11	9.20	5.95
Total debt	21.51	22.01	18.16	18.65	13.42
Firm age	51.34	53.34	43.07	45.07	29.31

Notes: (1) The table shows average values of firm-level variables for acquirers and targets in the pre- and post-merger years. (2) The average values for the potential controls are for all years in the sample period. (3) Values for total assets, revenue, employee count and total debt are log values.

Figure 1. Distribution of acquirers and targets over time.

⁸ For some firms, R&D intensities greater than one were found, suggesting higher R&D expenditures than revenues. These values are not implausible, especially in sectors such as pharmaceuticals or biotechnology, so they were kept in the sample. However, as per Szücs (2014), to prevent any bias in the estimated coefficients due to potential outliers, we capped R&D intensity values at 0.5.

From Table 2, one can see that merging firms investigated by the EC have greater total assets, revenue and debt and more employees than the average potential control firm. Comparing R&D metrics, acquirers typically have greater R&D growth than the potential controls and targets have lower R&D growth than the potential controls pre-merger but greater R&D growth post-merger. When controlling for size, R&D intensities are comparable across merging firms and potential controls.

Due to many discrepancies between the acquirers and targets' and potential controls' summary statistics, it appears that the average firm involved in a merger which has been scrutinised by the EC is different from the average firm which reports R&D expenditures. This means that for one to be able to infer any effects of M&A activity on innovation, appropriate non-merging control groups must be created.

3.2 Matching: Why Appropriate Control Groups are Required

The methodology used aims to isolate the causal effect of mergers on R&D outcomes. Ideally, one would observe both the actual and counterfactual scenarios for each merging firm. For example, consider Apple acquiring a target firm in a deal cleared by the EC. In a perfect setting, one would compare the post-merger R&D performance of Apple – after the acquisition – against a hypothetical Apple which did not acquire the target. Using a DiD estimator, the effect of the acquisition on Apple's R&D intensity and growth could be measured by calculating the difference between the two scenarios. In practice, however, both worlds are not observable; one only sees a world in which Apple either completes or does not complete the acquisition.

Studies estimating the causal effect of a treatment on a group of firms face the problem of not knowing what would have happened if the treatment had not occurred (Szücs, 2014). This is the missing counterfactual problem.

Following notation in Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983), if we denote the outcome of firm i receiving treatment (i.e., being a merging party) by r_i^1 and the outcome if they did not receive treatment (they did not merge) by r_i^0 , then the individual treatment effect is given by:

$$\Delta_i = r_i^1 - r_i^0.$$

Since only one of these outcomes is observable, one faces a missing data problem in estimating the individual treatment effect.

Experimental studies overcome this issue by *randomly* assigning one group of observations to treatment, while the other group of observations does not receive treatment. This approach was first introduced in Fisher (1935). Due to random assignment, properties are expected to be the same between the treatment and control group, other than the fact that one group was assigned treatment. The difference in outcomes between the two groups can then be attributed to the effect of receiving treatment. This is called the average treatment effect (ATE):

$$ATE_{\text{exp}} = E(r_i^1 - r_i^0).$$

Non-experimental studies face the challenge that an appropriate control group is difficult to find because the decision to receive treatment is not randomly determined by an experimenter. In the case of mergers, treatment of merging is decided by a firm's management so the assignment of firms to treated and control groups cannot be deemed random (Szücs, 2014). Therefore, in addition to the missing data problem, one faces the issue of endogeneity where the decision to receive treatment is determined by firm-specific characteristics which could also influence the treatment effect. Ignoring this could result in biased results because the effects which have been attributed to treatment could be due to other factors.

As stated earlier, merging firms in our sample are larger than the average potential control firm. Failing to acknowledge and account for this risks incorrectly ascribing observed effects to the merger when they may result from firm-size characteristics. To address this challenge, a control group with the same pre-merger characteristics as the treatment groups must be constructed. This ensures that control firms exhibit the same ex-ante probability of engaging in merger activity (either as acquirers or targets) as the firms that participated in mergers.

When conducting non-experimental studies, proper estimation of the ATE requires that the treated and control groups be comparable across all relevant characteristics, denoted by the vector c_i :

$$ATE_{\text{nonexp}} = E(r_i^1 - r_i^0 | c_i) = E(r_i^1 | c_i) - E(r_i^0 | c_i).$$

Thus, a sample needs to be constructed where merger involvement is not determined by specific firm characteristics – essentially making treatment random. If successful, this creates an appropriate control group for estimating the ATE and eliminates the self-selection problem. In this study, we accomplish this through various matching techniques.

3.3 Matching: Measures of Similarity and Selection Algorithms

A common approach in the literature, including Szücs (2014), to address the missing data and self-selection problem is to construct a control group using a matching procedure and DiD estimation.

Matching procedures consist of two steps. First, a measure of similarity must be calculated for both treated and untreated firms. Then, using an algorithm, one selects a relevant control group based on the similarity measure.

In this study, two different measures of similarity are used: propensity scores and a vector-norm-based measure, along with two matching algorithms: nearest-neighbour (NN) matching and caliper matching. The baseline control group is constructed using propensity scores with NN matching. Additionally, two further control groups are created, which are used as robustness checks to the baseline group: vector-norm with NN as a robustness check for the measure of similarity and propensity scores with caliper matching as a check for the selection algorithm. The same DiD estimator is used across all curated control groups.

The propensity score represents the conditional probability that an observation receives a particular treatment, based on its observable characteristics (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983). By matching treated observations with control observations based on propensity scores, one obtains two groups which do not differ with respect to the observable characteristics that the propensity scores were calculated upon (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1985). Thus, propensity score matching (PSM) dramatically reduces heterogeneity between treated and control groups.

As an alternative to PSM, a vector-norm based measure treats observable characteristics as a normalised vector and calculates the distance between the vector of each treated observation and all vectors of the potential control observations (Abadie, et al., 2004).

For both measures, data from the pre-merger year of treatment is used in the similarity score calculation to ensure that the merger effects do not impact the matching.

Once the measure is created, NN and caliper matching algorithms are used to construct the control groups. NN matching pairs each treated firm with the control firm that has the closest matching measure. Therefore, the matched firm is the one most like the merging firm based on its characteristics in the pre-merger year. Each merging firm is assigned a unique match as control firms are not replaced once they are selected. Resultantly, the control group is the same size as the treated group.

In caliper matching, each treated observation is paired with multiple control observations. In this study, each treated firm is matched to three controls with the most similar propensity scores, given the scores do not differ by more than 0.038.⁹ As each treatment gets matched to a maximum of three controls, the resulting control group is larger than the treatment group.

NN and caliper matching face a trade-off between variance and bias in the estimates. Variance decreases when we make the control group larger, but at the cost of increased bias.¹⁰ We use the variety of matching methods to assess whether this trade-off has material impacts on our results.

3.4 Matching: Results

The characteristics used to calculate propensity scores are factors which could influence the decision to merge, as well as influence future R&D incentives. These are: R&D intensity, R&D growth, total assets, total employees, profitability, debt and firm age. In line with Szücs (2014), to account for potential nonlinearities in size and age, polynomial terms are included into the calculation for the total assets and age terms. For acquirers and targets separately,

⁹ We determine a caliper of 0.038 following the suggestion of Rosenbaum and Rubin (1985) to choose a caliper of size $c = 0.25 \times [(s_1^2 + s_0^2)/2]^{1/2}$, where s_1^2 (s_0^2) is the variance of the propensity scores in the treated (control) group.

¹⁰ See Caliendo and Kopeinig (2008) for a discussion on the variance-bias trade-offs in matching procedures.

the dependent variable is a dummy indicating if a firm merged in the proceeding period. The estimated probit model results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Propensity score estimation (probit model)

	Acquirers		Targets	
R&D intensity	1.838***	(0.348)	0.605	(0.744)
R&D growth	-0.085	(0.093)	-0.190	(0.221)
Total assets	1.594***	(0.438)	1.916**	(0.966)
Total assets ²	-0.030**	(0.009)	-0.038*	(0.021)
Employees	0.222***	(0.022)	0.101**	(0.047)
Profitability	1.710***	(0.257)	-0.796	(0.539)
Total debt	0.026*	(0.011)	-0.019*	(0.011)
Firm age	0.001	(0.001)	0.004	(0.004)
Firm age ²	0.000	(0.000)	0.000	(0.000)
Observations	213591		213342	
Pseudo-R ²	0.34		0.20	
Treatment firms	277		27	

*Standard errors in parentheses, $p < 0.1$

**Standard errors in parentheses, $p < 0.05$

***Standard errors in parentheses, $p < 0.01$

From Table 3, one can see that acquiring firms are, on average, significantly more R&D intensive, have more total assets, employees and debt and higher profitability than non-merging firms. Neither R&D growth nor firm age are statistically significant determinants for being an acquirer. The negative coefficient of the squared total asset term suggests an inverse U-shaped relationship between total assets and the probability of being an acquirer.

The probit estimation for target firms provides less statistically significant results, which may be due to the smaller sample size of target firms. However, one sees that, on average, target firms have more assets and employees and less debt than non-target firms. There is also an inverse U-shaped relationship between total assets and the probability of being a target.

Using the probit outputs, two control groups are created using the calculated propensity scores and the third control group is created with the vector-norm approach, for both acquirers and targets. Following this, it is important to check whether a balanced sample is obtained between the treatment groups and their curated control groups. Balance means that the characteristics between the groups do not differ systematically, which is required to ascertain the ATE for non-experimental studies (see Section 3.2).

The standardised biases before and after the respective matching procedures are tabulated in Table 4, as well as the reduction in bias achieved by the matching. See Appendix B for a more intuitive visualisation of the bias reductions. The standardised bias¹¹ is the bias one incurs by comparing treated and non-treated firms across their characteristics. As can be seen from the first column of Table 4, the initial biases were high, meaning treated and non-treated firms did not share similar characteristics.

Table 4. Standardised biases of characteristics before and after matching

	Initial bias (%)	PSM NN		PSM Caliper		Vector norm NN	
		Bias (%)	Reduction (%)	Bias (%)	Reduction (%)	Bias (%)	Reduction (%)
Acquirers							
R&D intensity	5.40	3.19	40.93	11.85	-119.44	16.66	-208.52
R&D growth	4.32	10.27	-137.73	8.54	-97.69	0.18	95.83
Total assets	339.28	10.19	97.00	6.90	97.97	8.28	97.56
Total assets ²	300.26	10.26	96.58	6.45	97.85	8.3	97.24
Employees	315.92	7.31	97.69	12.56	96.02	8.97	97.16
Profitability	74.42	10.65	85.69	0.13	99.83	16.19	78.24
Total debt	302.92	0.64	99.79	2.96	99.02	1.12	99.63
Firm age	50.25	9.25	81.59	2.31	95.40	4.26	91.52
Firm age ²	48.08	8.57	82.18	1.61	96.65	4.79	90.04
Targets							
R&D intensity	2.30	2.12	7.83	23.32	-913.91	8.81	-282.26
R&D growth	9.54	2.91	69.50	15.17	-59.01	0.78	91.85
Total assets	282.92	4.33	98.47	5.74	97.97	19.42	93.13
Total assets ²	253.68	5.25	97.93	6.26	97.53	17.85	92.97
Employees	209.34	13.26	93.67	15.66	92.52	6.9	96.71
Profitability	8.98	29.86	-232.52	7.27	19.04	7.24	19.43
Total debt	94.82	11.65	87.71	22.53	76.24	0.22	99.77
Firm age	53.28	4.16	92.19	7.27	86.35	3.9	92.7
Firm age ²	49.76	5.46	89.03	4.91	90.13	6.5	86.93

From Table 4, one can see that all three matching approaches largely eliminate biases between the treated and non-treated firms, which form the control groups. Most standardised biases are reduced to below 10%. Rubin (2001) and Stuart (2010) suggest that post-matching, standardised biases should not exceed 25%. This criterion is met for all characteristics between treatment and created control groups – other than for target profitability with PSM and NN, which is likely due to the small sample size of targets creating

¹¹ The standardised bias is calculated as $(\bar{X}_t - \bar{X}_c)/\sigma_t$. This is the difference in means of the treatment (\bar{X}_t) and control group (\bar{X}_c) divided by the standard deviation of the treatment group (σ_t). Before matching, the control group refers to all potential controls. Post-matching, the control group refers to the controls selected via the matching.

less statistically significant propensity scores. Note that the matching procedure increases the bias for some characteristics. However, this comes at a benefit of reducing the bias of other characteristics. Overall, the decrease in standardised biases allows for the conclusion that the matching procedures have removed the observable heterogeneity between treatment and control groups in the characteristics which are employed in the creation of the matching metrics.

Finally, the overlap is checked between the respective acquirers' and targets' control groups. For both acquirers and targets, there is a moderate overlap between the control observations selected by the PSM NN and PSM caliper algorithms (44.0% for acquirers and 34.9% for targets). The overlap between the PSM NN and vector-norm NN algorithms is smaller (19.8% for acquirers and 1.9% for targets), as is the overlap between the PSM caliper and vector-norm NN algorithms (18.4% for acquirers and 0% for targets). This variation suggests that although some approaches select similar firms – especially in the case of acquirers – the variation across the control groups is sufficient to warrant separate analyses.

3.5 Structural Zeros

A potential source of bias arises from structural zeros in accounting data on R&D expenditure. While not all firms report R&D expenditures,¹² some report “zero” due to minimal or no innovative activities. Many studies exclude these firms, but doing so may bias results by focusing only on innovative firms. There is the possibility that the impact of mergers on innovation differs systematically between firms with positive R&D and those with zero R&D. To avoid this bias, this sample includes both types of firms, with 19% of merging firms explicitly reporting zero R&D expenditures in the pre-merger period.

¹² See Dionysiou, et al., (2023) for a report on practices for reporting R&D expenditures.

3.6 Difference-in-Differences Strategy

Having created the relevant control groups, the effects of mergers on R&D growth and intensity are estimated using DiD estimators. To do this, we construct time windows around each merger, using observations from the merging firms and their matched controls during the periods $[t - 3, t - 1]$ and $[t + 1, t + 6]$, where t refers to the year of the merger. The period (t) is not included in the estimators to avoid measurement of consolidation effects. By including a set of dummy variables indicating whether a firm was involved in a merger one year ago, two years ago, and so on, the changes in the R&D metrics are tracked over time.

Starting with the R&D intensity estimator, additional dummies are included for all treated observations to control for unobserved differences between treated and control groups. We estimate the following models for acquirers and targets respectively:

$$rdint_{ij} = \alpha + \sum_{t=1}^6 \beta_t \text{acquirer}_{i,j-t} + \delta \text{treat_acq} + \eta \text{controls} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

$$rdint_{ij} = \alpha + \sum_{t=1}^6 \gamma_t \text{target}_{i,j-t} + \zeta \text{treat_tar} + \eta \text{controls} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

The R&D intensity of firm i in year j is regressed on a set of merger dummies from the year after the merger ($t = 1$) up to six years after the merger ($t = 6$), with separate regressions for the acquirer and the target. In Szücs (2014), acquirers and targets are pooled into a single regression, with a dummy variable indicating whether a firm is an acquirer or a target. This pooling does not affect the Szücs' results. In contrast, this study runs separate regressions for acquirers and targets, which allows for a more intuitive interpretation of the DiD estimators.

Industry, country and time effects are controlled for in the estimators. The β_t (γ_t) coefficients capture how much the acquirers' (targets') R&D intensity deviates from that of the control group in each period. This is interpreted as the treatment effect of the merger on R&D intensity.

For the R&D growth estimator, the dependent variable is a growth rate and so controls for individual fixed effects are not required. Therefore, the acquirer/target dummy is excluded from the regression. We estimate the following models:

$$\text{rdgrowth}_{ij} = \alpha + \sum_{t=1}^6 \beta_t \text{acquirer}_{i,j-t} + \eta \text{controls} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

$$\text{rdgrowth}_{ij} = \alpha + \sum_{t=1}^6 \gamma_t \text{target}_{i,j-t} + \eta \text{controls} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Like before, the β_t (γ_t) coefficients capture how much the acquirers' (targets') R&D growth deviates from that of the control group in each period. The same controls as in the R&D intensity regression are used.

4 Results

4.1 Mean Changes in R&D

Before looking at the DiD estimators' outputs, the mean R&D intensity and growth around the time of the merger are considered.

The mean R&D growth for acquirers and targets around the time of the merger is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. R&D growth of acquirers and targets in the years around the merger

Prior to the merger, acquirers experience average R&D growth rates of 4.7 – 8.0%. In the year of the merger, average R&D growth rises to 11.8%, but drops in the year immediately after to 10.8%. This decreases further in the proceeding years, as growth rates decline significantly to 4.3% by the second-year post-merger and remain around this level in the subsequent years.

The spike in the merger period could be attributed to consolidation effects, where R&D assets from the target are transferred to the acquirer's books. This effect is due to accounting practices and not innovation impacts from mergers. Hence, the year of the merger ($t = 0$) is excluded from the DiD estimators.

For target firms, average R&D growth exhibits greater volatility compared to that of acquirers. Two years prior to being acquired, average R&D growth among targets is 13.6%. However, this drops sharply to 0.01% in the year preceding the merger and remains at that level during the year of the merger. In the two subsequent years, R&D growth rises to 8.9% and 13.3%, respectively. In later years, the growth rate continues to fluctuate, alternating between positive and negative growth rates. This observed volatility is likely attributable to the small sample size of target firms.

The mean R&D intensities of acquirers and targets around the time of the merger are plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. R&D intensity of acquirers and targets in the years around the merger

As can be seen for acquirers, average R&D intensity remains relatively stable at approximately 3.7% in the years leading up to the merger. In the year of the merger, it increases modestly to 3.8%, maintaining this level in the following year. By year ($t + 2$), R&D intensity rises marginally to 3.9%, but then declines below the pre-merger level, reaching 3.6% by year ($t + 4$). From year ($t + 5$) onwards, R&D intensity levels show signs of recovery.

In contrast, prior to the merger, on average, target firms display R&D intensities averaging 3.4 – 3.6%. However, in the merger year, this falls significantly to 2.0% and it declines further to 1.8% in the following year. Subsequently, average R&D intensities follow an increasing trend over the next five years, peaking at 2.2% in year ($t + 6$).

While Figure 2 and Figure 3 suggest certain changes in innovative behaviour occur around a merger, they only represent average values, which do not allow for causality interpretations. To achieve this, the DiD estimators are employed using the relevant control groups, with the results presented in Section 4.2.

4.2 Difference-in-Differences Results

All regressions are conducted independently to find the effects on acquirers and targets separately with the three different control samples obtained by “PSM NN”, “PSM caliper” and “vector-norm NN” matching methods. While all models include controls for industry, country of headquarter and year, the effects of these controls are not reported, as the focus is on the collective outcomes for all firms. The results for R&D growth and R&D intensity are reported in Table 5 and in Table 6 respectively. Intuitive visualisations for all regression outputs can be found in Appendix C.

Table 5. R&D growth of acquirers and targets from $t + 1$ to $t + 6$

	PS NN matching		PS Caliper matching		Vector-norm NN matching	
Acquirer t+1	0.041*	(0.021)	0.068***	(0.016)	0.089***	(0.024)
Acquirer t+2	-0.026	(0.024)	-0.018	(0.019)	-0.026	(0.027)
Acquirer t+3	0.000	(0.020)	-0.010	(0.019)	-0.019	(0.029)
Acquirer t+4	-0.054*	(0.028)	-0.042**	(0.017)	-0.016	(0.023)
Acquirer t+5	-0.014	(0.023)	0.003	(0.024)	0.015	(0.023)
Acquirer t+6	0.030	(0.025)	0.006	(0.020)	-0.004	(0.025)
Observations	3724		4752		3716	
Acquirers	277		277		277	
Σ Acquirer timeline ^a	0.001		0.000		0.001	
Target t+1	-0.010	(0.060)	-0.013	(0.068)	0.011	(0.092)
Target t+2	-0.029	(0.062)	-0.032	(0.052)	0.082	(0.120)
Target t+3	-0.007	(0.052)	-0.056	(0.054)	-0.110	(0.127)
Target t+4	0.011	(0.125)	0.009	(0.101)	-0.101	(0.111)
Target t+5	-0.261*	(0.139)	-0.216*	(0.113)	-0.248*	(0.139)
Target t+6	0.071	(0.071)	-0.066	(0.058)	-0.160	(0.113)
Observations	368		541		313	
Targets	27		27		27	
Σ Target timeline ^a	0.610		0.398		0.207	

Notes: All regressions include controls for industry, country and year. Standard errors (in parenthesis) are robust and allow for clustering on the year-level.

* $p < 0.1$

** $p < 0.05$

*** $p < 0.01$

^a p -Values of the Wald-test with the null-hypothesis that the sum of timeline coefficients of acquirers (or targets) is not statistically different from zero.

Table 5 shows that in the year following a merger, acquirers experience a statistically significant increase in R&D growth, ranging from 4.1 to 8.9 percentage points across samples, significant at the 10% level or better. However, beyond the year post-merger, acquirers' R&D growths do not differ significantly from those of the control groups. The only exceptions are negative coefficients observed in year $(t + 4)$ under the PSM NN and PSM caliper matching approaches. Additionally, there is no consistent pattern in the sign of the coefficients after the first year, aside from recurring negative coefficients in years $(t + 2)$ and $(t + 4)$.

For target firms, most R&D growth rates are not statistically different from those of the control groups. The only exception occurs in year $(t + 5)$, where all samples exhibit negative and statistically significant coefficients. Aside from this, no other coefficients are statistically significant, and there is limited consistency in the direction of effects, though negative coefficients across all samples are observed in years $(t + 3)$ and $(t + 5)$.

The p -values reported at the bottom of each acquirer and target section assess the null-hypothesis that the sum of all acquirer or target timeline coefficients are not statistically different from zero. For acquirers, all hypotheses can be rejected at the 1% level, whereas for targets the level of significance varies across samples.

Table 6. R&D intensity of acquirers and targets from $t + 1$ to $t + 6$

	PS NN matching		PS Caliper matching		Vector-norm NN matching	
Acquirer t+1	-0.008	(0.006)	0.001	(0.004)	0.001	(0.003)
Acquirer t+2	-0.006	(0.005)	0.003	(0.003)	0.001	(0.003)
Acquirer t+3	-0.003	(0.005)	0.005	(0.004)	0.002	(0.003)
Acquirer t+4	-0.008	(0.006)	0.002	(0.004)	-0.002	(0.004)
Acquirer t+5	-0.003	(0.006)	0.006	(0.005)	0.003	(0.003)
Acquirer t+6	-0.004	(0.005)	0.005	(0.004)	0.002	(0.003)
Acquirer	-0.007*	(0.003)	-0.008**	(0.002)	-0.013***	(0.002)
Observations	3739		4782		3740	
Acquirers	277		277		277	
Σ Acquirer timeline ^a	0.504		0.617		0.905	
Target t+1	-0.016	(0.012)	-0.016	(0.017)	-0.040*	(0.022)
Target t+2	-0.008	(0.010)	-0.007	(0.014)	-0.007	(0.018)
Target t+3	-0.008	(0.008)	-0.003	(0.011)	-0.000	(0.015)
Target t+4	-0.008	(0.012)	-0.008	(0.011)	-0.021	(0.015)
Target t+5	-0.018	(0.015)	-0.015	(0.013)	-0.006	(0.014)
Target t+6	-0.016	(0.016)	-0.017	(0.015)	-0.020	(0.014)
Target	0.014	(0.010)	0.015	(0.014)	-0.046***	(0.016)
Observations	370		544		316	
Targets	27		27		27	
Σ Target timeline ^a	0.591		0.900		0.544	

Notes: All regressions include controls for industry, country and year. Standard errors (in parenthesis) are robust and allow for clustering on the year-level.

* $p < 0.1$

** $p < 0.05$

*** $p < 0.01$

^a p -Values of the Wald-test with the null-hypothesis that the sum of timeline coefficients of acquirers (or targets) is not statistically different from zero.

Turning to Table 6, one can observe that in the baseline control group (PSM NN matching), on average, the R&D intensity of acquirers appears to be negatively affected by mergers, as indicated by negative coefficients across all time periods. However, these coefficients are not statistically significant and the negative pattern is not consistent across the matching samples.

For target firms, all coefficients are negative, suggesting a decline in R&D intensity following mergers. Nevertheless, these effects are not statistically significant, except for under the vector-norm NN matching approach in the year following the merger.

As with the R&D growth regressions, we report the p -values of the hypothesis that the sum of all reported coefficients is not statistically different from zero. None of the null hypotheses can be rejected at any level of statistical significance.

5 Discussion

5.1 What can be Inferred from the Results?

First, the results suggests that merger targets are chosen on the basis that they are innovative firms, as indicated by their average R&D intensity of 3.6% pre-merger. The high ratio of R&D expenditure to revenue for targets supports the notion that targets have not yet fully capitalised on the commerciality of their innovative efforts. Meanwhile, acquirers appear to select targets with attractive technological portfolios that have yet to be commercially exploited (Szücs, 2014). In contrast to targets, acquirers are, on average, larger and more profitable firms.

When examining the impact of mergers on R&D levels post-merger, the results obtained show that, on average, acquirers experience an increase in R&D growth in the year following the merger. This effect remains robust across all control groups and follows the results found in Stiebale (2013). One possible explanation for this is that acquirers, once merged with the target, make a one-time increase in R&D expenditures to integrate the target's innovative activities and to enhance the combined firm's innovative efforts. However, the same effect is not observed in merger targets. This suggests that the impact is heterogeneous, occurring in cases where targets are fully integrated into the acquiring firm rather than remaining separate entities. These results may follow from the conclusions of Puranam and Srikanth (2007), which found that integration enables acquirers to leverage the acquired firm's existing knowledge as an input for their own innovation.

When looking at the R&D growth rates in years after the post-merger year, the results are not statistically significant – except for targets, which experience statistically significant negative impacts in the year ($t + 5$). Therefore, definitive conclusions cannot be drawn.

A similar lack of statistical significance is observed in the results for R&D intensity changes post-merger. For acquirers, except for the baseline control group – which reveals a non-statistically significant negative effect of mergers on the R&D intensities of acquirers in all years following a merger – all other results for acquirers vary. Although the effect of the baseline group is not robust across all control groups, it may support the notion of technology-

driven acquisitions. Rather than pursuing the necessary R&D for innovative projects in-house, acquirers may opt to purchase firms that are developing or have already developed new technologies. The post-merger period then reflects the acquirer exploiting the target's innovation and commercialising it, thereby increasing their own sales (Szücs, 2014).

5.2 Why might the Results be Statistically Insignificant?

Aside from the finding that acquirers increase R&D growth in year $(t + 1)$, all other results are either statistically insignificant or are not robust across all control groups. There are several possible explanations for this which can be proposed.

First, the sample used consists of mergers that were investigated by the EC but ultimately cleared outright or cleared with conditions – the latter meaning the acquirer was required to implement structural remedies or behavioural remedies. While there is always the possibility of a type II error in the EC's decision making (meaning an anti-competitive merger was cleared) – and we do not deny that such cases can occur – one would expect a large proportion of cleared mergers to pose no significant impact on competitive outcomes. This raises the question of whether one should expect to find a statistically significant effect on innovation – other than perhaps a positive effect – from the sample.

Another potential explanation could be because the sample studied consists of mergers across various industries and countries. This study searches for an average effect across *all* mergers, irrespective of industry and country. Whilst there are merits to this, most empirical studies with statistically significant results focus on specific industries or countries, where effects may be more homogenous. Given the wide range of industries and countries used in the sample, it is reasonable to question whether one should expect consistent effects on innovation across the variety of contexts. Additionally, due to the considerable number of countries and industries represented in this sample, in which each subgroup is small, it would be difficult to identify any specific treatment effects on industry and country.

Finally, it is important to acknowledge that each merger is unique. Firms are heterogeneous – they are different sizes, operate in different product markets and pursue different innovative projects. As such, no two combinations of firms are identical. This leads to the

question of whether one should expect statistically significant effects to be found on a sample of all mergers. While many of the coefficients found in the results are negative, they are statistically insignificant, indicating that the observed trends do not consistently hold across a substantial number of firms.

5.3 Why do the Results of this Study Differ from Szücs (2014)?

Having discussed reasons for the statistically insignificant results in this study, it is now important to consider why the findings differ from those of Szücs (2014), whose methodology yielded statistically significant results. Szücs (2014) found statistically significant negative effects in targets' R&D growth rates and in both acquirers and targets' R&D intensities in the years following a merger, which were robust across all control samples. In contrast, this study does not match these findings.

First, Szücs (2014) focuses on mergers investigated by the EC and by the FTC between 1990 and 2010. The study in this dissertation, however, only examines mergers investigated by the EC and between 1997 and 2023. While the difference in years of mergers investigated is unlikely to account for the discrepancy – since even when restricting the sample to pre-2010 cases, the results remain statistically insignificant – this study's focus on EC cases may be a contributing factor. The FTC publishes communications on only a selective subset of notified mergers which it chooses to investigate, leading to a different sample of mergers compared to those in Szücs (2014).

Additionally, the sample of target firms used in this study is smaller than Szücs' due to data availability constraints, particularly for post-merger information of target firms in the Moody's Orbis dataset. Szücs (2014), on the other hand, has a larger proportion of US-headquartered firms, which may have better accounting data coverage that is readily available.

Another difference is that in Szücs (2014), results are consistent across control groups. For this study, coefficients which are statistically significant in the baseline scenario of PSM with NN matching are often not statistically significant with the other control groups constructed

with other matching techniques. An explanation for this could be an insufficient sample of potential controls for the various matching techniques to be taken from.

6 Conclusions and Suggestions for Future Research

This study attempts to estimate the effects of mergers on R&D growth as well as intensity for both acquirers and target firms, using a sample of mergers that were investigated by the EC between 1997 and 2023.

Regarding the methodology, this study followed a popular approach in the literature which combines matching techniques with DiD estimation. Additionally, the robustness of the findings is assessed by using two different matching scores and two distinct matching algorithms. However, the results across the three matched samples are not entirely consistent, indicating that the choice of control group can significantly influence the findings.

The results obtained suggest that acquirers tend to select highly innovative targets, as indicated by the high R&D intensities of targets. This pattern implies that acquirers seek firms with promising technological portfolios that have not yet been fully commercialised. In the year following an acquisition, acquirers tend to experience an increase in R&D growth, which may be due to efforts to integrate the target's innovative activities and enhance their own innovation capacity. In contrast, targets do not exhibit a similar boost in R&D growth, implying that the effect is more pronounced when targets are fully integrated into the acquiring firm. Changes in R&D growth after the first-year post-merger are statistically insignificant, along with the consensus of results on R&D intensity. These findings highlight the heterogeneity of merger effects, which vary depending on the firm.

In terms of policy implications, the overarching conclusion of this study is that there is no homogenous effect of mergers on innovation incentives. As a result, each merger should be assessed on its individual merits. While the EC already conducts case-by-case assessments, it is important to emphasise that not all mergers impede innovation inputs. Acknowledgement of this is critical for ensuring that regulatory decisions are tailored to the specific characteristics of each merger.

This study contributes to the growing body of empirical evidence on the impact of mergers on innovation. However, there are several avenues for further research.

While this study primarily focuses on the effects of mergers on innovation inputs (R&D growth and intensity), future research could explore the effects on innovation outputs, like patents. This would help clarify whether mergers have impacts on innovation outputs. From a methodological perspective, patent counts or cites are a useful outcome to look at because if one fails to match a firm to any patents, one can be certain that the firm does not have patents. In contrast, the absence of reported R&D expenditures does not necessarily indicate that a firm has not conducted any R&D, making patents a more definitive indicator in such cases.

Another interesting direction would be to examine the impact of mergers not only on acquirers and targets but also on competitors. Although Valentini (2016) and Haucap et al. (2019) explore this, their studies suffer from sample biases. A more refined methodology could address this issue, particularly by focusing on smaller firms which are less likely to be competitors to multiple mergers within given periods and acknowledging that the results are based upon data from smaller firms.

Lastly, future research could investigate differences in innovation incentives between mergers that were cleared outright and those cleared with remedies by the EC. Since mergers requiring remedies supposedly pose a greater threat to competition than mergers cleared outright, it would be valuable to examine whether this difference has an impact on innovation, even after the remedies are applied. One could use a similar methodology as that in this study but add binary variables indicating if a merger was subject to behavioural or structural remedies. Such research could function as a test to explore the effectiveness of EC decisions.

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Appendices

A Detailed Sample Summary Statistics

Table A1. Distribution of firm headquarters by country in the sample (n=304)

Country/Region	Count	% of Sample
United States	92	30.3%
Germany	33	10.9%
France	26	8.6%
Japan	23	7.6%
United Kingdom	19	6.3%
Sweden	13	4.3%
Switzerland	10	3.3%
Belgium	9	3.0%
Ireland	9	3.0%
Italy	9	3.0%
Netherlands	8	2.6%
Denmark	6	2.0%
Finland	6	2.0%
Other (18 countries)	41	13.5%

Notes: The table reports unique firms. Firms acting as acquirers in multiple years spaced more than four years apart are counted once in this distribution, but multiple times in the total acquirer count.

Table A2. Distribution of firm 2-digit US SIC codes in the sample (n=304)

US SIC code	Industry Description	Count	% of Sample
28	Chemicals and Allied Products	51	16.8%
36	Electronic & Other Electrical Equipment & Components	28	9.2%
37	Transportation Equipment	25	8.2%
35	Industrial and Commercial Machinery and Computer Equipment	22	7.2%
38	Measuring, Photographic, Medical, & Optical Goods, & Clocks	21	6.9%
73	Business Services	19	6.3%
33	Primary Metal Industries	16	5.3%
48	Communications	14	4.6%
20	Food and Kindred Products	13	4.3%
10	Metal Mining	11	3.6%
50	Wholesale Trade - Durable Goods	10	3.3%
49	Electric, Gas and Sanitary Services	9	3.0%
13	Oil and Gas Extraction	7	2.3%
26	Paper and Allied Products	7	2.3%
32	Stone, Clay, Glass, and Concrete Products	6	2.0%
Other	Other Industries (19 sectors)	45	14.8%

Notes: The table reports unique firms. Firms acting as acquirers in multiple years spaced more than four years apart are counted once in this distribution, but multiple times in the total acquirer count.

B Visualisation of Bias Reductions from Matching

B1. PSM and NN for acquirers

B2. PSM and NN for targets

B3. PSM and caliper for acquirers

B4. PSM and caliper for targets

B5. Vector norm and NN for acquirers

B6. Vector norm and NN for targets

- Standardised bias of matched sample
- Standardised bias of unmatched sample

Notes: (1) White points represent the standardised biases of the sample before matching. (2) Black points represent the standardised biases of the control samples after matching. (3) The vertical lines show bias levels of 0.05 and 0.1, respectively.

Figure B. Bias reductions for matched samples compared to all potential controls

C Visualisations of DiD Estimates

C1.A. PSM and NN for acquirers

C1.B. PSM and caliper for acquirers

C1.C. Vector norm and NN for acquirers

Notes: The points show the DiD estimate for each given year respective to the merger. The bars show the 90% confidence intervals. Any bar that crosses zero indicates that the coefficient is not statistically significant at the 10% level.

Figure C1. DiD estimates for R&D growth of acquirers in the years following a merger

C2.A. PSM and NN for targets

C2.B. PSM and caliper for targets

C2.C. Vector norm and NN for targets

Notes: The points show the DiD estimate for each given year respective to the merger. The bars show the 90% confidence intervals. Any bar that crosses zero indicates that the coefficient is not statistically significant at the 10% level.

Figure C2. DiD estimates for R&D growth of targets in the years following a merger

C3.A. PSM and NN for acquirers

C3.B. PSM and caliper for acquirers

C3.C. Vector norm and NN for acquirers

Notes: The points show the DiD estimate for each given year respective to the merger. The bars show the 90% confidence intervals. Any bar that crosses zero indicates that the coefficient is not statistically significant at the 10% level.

Figure C3. DiD estimates for R&D intensity of acquirers in the years following a merger

C4.A. PSM and NN for targets

C4.B. PSM and caliper for targets

C4.C. Vector norm and NN for targets

Notes: The points show the DiD estimate for each given year respective to the merger. The bars show the 90% confidence intervals. Any bar that crosses zero indicates that the coefficient is not statistically significant at the 10% level.

Figure C4. DiD estimates for R&D intensity of targets in the years following a merger